

TEACHING COMPETENCE OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS AND ITS INFLUENCE ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

This study sought to establish the competence of Senior High School teachers in relation to learners' academic performance in Negros Oriental High School for the first and second quarters of school year 2019-2020. It utilized descriptive research design and employed the stratified random sampling technique using Slovin's formula in identifying the 255 respondents (Grade 11 and 12) from the total population of 702. To analyze the data, the study employed a validated questionnaire. It utilized a range of statistical methods, including frequency counts, percentages, means, and non-parametric tests such as the Mann-Whitney U test, Kruskal-Wallis H test, and Spearman's rho. The significant findings revealed that the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of instructional delivery and assessment delivery are both at "great extent". In contrast, the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of classroom management is at a "moderate extent". On the other hand, the extent of teaching competence in instructional delivery and assessment delivery when grouped according to age, sex, and track are at "great extent". However, in classroom management, competence varied by group. Furthermore, it was found that there is a significant difference in the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers when grouped and compared according to age, and there is no significant difference when grouped according to sex and track. Lastly, it was found that there is a significant relationship between the extent of teaching competence and the level of learners' academic performance.

Keywords: *teaching competence, academic performance, instructional delivery, classroom management, assessment delivery*

INTRODUCTION

Teachers' skills and knowledge, often referred to as competencies, are fundamental to their effectiveness. To maximize student learning in today's complex classrooms, teachers need expertise in areas like curriculum development, differentiated instruction, and classroom management, requiring them to make hundreds of crucial decisions daily (Naz, 2016). However, simply recognizing the importance of these skills isn't enough. To ensure quality education for all, we need to establish a clear link between a teacher's competency and student achievement through solid evidence (Bilasa, 2017).

This highlights the need to examine how teacher competencies may be impacting student achievement, particularly in schools facing achievement gaps.

Negros Oriental High School serves as a case study for this concern. In School Year 2018-2019, the grade summary revealed a significant disparity in knowledge distribution among senior high school students. This data exposes a concerning achievement gap that needs to be addressed. A key factor in tackling this gap is the ability of secondary teachers to effectively guide students. A study by Goldhaber et al. (2015) highlights a crucial point: disadvantaged students are more likely to have less qualified teachers. This lack of access to skilled educators can hinder academic progress and exacerbate existing achievement gaps.

Based on School Form 9, or the Learners' Report for the first grading period of the school year 2019-2020, a significant number of students fell below proficiency level, with average grades ranging from 78 to 82 percent. If education is delivered on an equal footing, what keeps these students lagging? These observations prompted the researcher to conduct this study.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the extent of the teaching competence of senior high school teachers and their influence on the students' academic performance of Negros Oriental High School for the first and second quarters of School Year 2019-2020. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of the following variables:
 - 1.1. Age;
 - 1.2. Sex; and
 - 1.3. Track?

2. What is the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by the students in terms of the following areas:
 - 2.1. Instructional Delivery;
 - 2.2. Classroom Management; and
 - 2.3. Assessment Delivery?

3. What is the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by the students and when they are grouped according to the aforementioned variables?
 4. What is the level of students' academic performance when they are grouped according to the aforementioned variables?
 5. Is there a significant difference in the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by the students and when they are grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables?
 6. Is there a significant difference in the level of students' academic performance when they are grouped and compared to the aforementioned variables?
 7. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of teaching competence and the level of students' academic performance?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive research design to investigate the relationship between the teaching competence of secondary school teachers and the academic performance of senior high school students at Negros Oriental High School during the first and second quarters of the 2019-2020 school year.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted at Negros Oriental High School (NOHS) in Dumaguete City, Philippines. Founded in 1902, NOHS is a cornerstone of the city's educational landscape. With over a century of experience, it has played a significant role in shaping the lives of countless students from Dumaguete City and the surrounding Negros Oriental province. The school's central location within Dumaguete City makes it readily accessible to students from various backgrounds, fostering a diverse student body.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were 255 from the total population of 702 Grade 11 and 12 Senior High School students enrolled at Negros Oriental High School (NOHS) for School Year 2019-2020. Since the total number of respondents is too large to handle, stratified random sampling using Slovin's formula was employed.

The selection of respondents was done through the lottery method, specifically the fishbowl technique wherein the researcher picked the corresponding number of samples from a bowl containing the complete list of students in the aforementioned tracks of offerings.

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents according to their grade level and track.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

Grade Level	Track	Population (N)	Percentage (%)	Sample (n)
11	GAS	31	4.42	11
	HUMSS	135	19.23	49
	ABM	48	6.84	17
	STEM	31	4.42	11
	TVL	134	19.09	49
	Arts & Design	25	3.56	9
	Sports	15	2.14	6
12	GAS	48	6.84	17
	HUMSS	83	11.82	30
	ABM	51	7.26	19
	STEM	24	3.42	9
	TVL	50	7.12	18
	Arts & Design	13	1.85	5
	Sports	14	1.99	5
Total		702	100.00	255

Data Gathering Instruments

In this study, the researcher used a self-made questionnaire to gather all the data, mainly from student respondents. The questionnaire consisted of 2 parts: Part 1 contains queries on respondents' profiles such as age, sex, grade level, and track, while Part 2 contains the questionnaire proper consisting of 30 items on teaching competencies of secondary school teachers, 10-line items per area.

The questionnaires were gathered and the results were recorded, analyzed, and treated. The respondents were asked to rate each item using the five-point Likert scale which contains the following scores: 5 – Very High; 4 – High; 3 – Moderate; 2 – Low and 1 – Very Low.

Validity

A research instrument's effectiveness hinges on its ability to measure what it's designed to assess accurately. This concept, known as validity, ensures the interpretations drawn from the data are well-founded. While achieving perfect validity is uncommon, researchers employ various techniques to evaluate the instrument's strength in different aspects.

This study implemented face and content validation to ensure the instrument captured the intended information. Face validity involved presenting the questionnaire to three education experts: one holding a Master's degree and two with a doctorate. These experts evaluated the clarity, relevance, and appropriateness of the questions. Their feedback and suggestions, particularly regarding the alignment of questions with the targeted construct, were incorporated into the final version of the instrument. Following this initial assessment, we conducted a content validation process to ensure the instrument aligned with the targeted construct in a more comprehensive manner.

The instrument validation for content validity was anchored from those developed by Oducado (2020), built upon the eight criteria set forth by Carter V. Good and Douglas V. Scates. This validation process confirms that the average rating of the three jurors was 4.77, which falls within the "excellent" range (4.04 – 5.00) on the established scale. This high rating suggests that the survey instrument possesses strong face and content validity.

Reliability

A research instrument's effectiveness relies on its ability to produce consistent results. This concept, known as reliability, ensures the instrument measures the same construct stably. Internal consistency, a key aspect of reliability, reflects how closely related individual items within an instrument are to the overall construct being measured.

This study assessed the internal consistency of the self-developed instrument using Cronbach's alpha, which provides a value between 0 and 1, with higher values indicating stronger internal consistency. While it remains a widely used measure, it's crucial to acknowledge its limitations, such as sensitivity to the number of items (Clark & Watson, 2019).

To assess the instrument's internal consistency in this regard, a pilot test was conducted with 30 senior high school students from the same school, excluding them from the final sample population. The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient for the pilot test was 0.932, which suggests a high level of internal consistency for the instrument.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathered from the responses of the respondents were tallied and tabulated using the appropriate statistical tools. The raw data was transformed into

numerical code guided by a coding manual. This allows computer processing, statistical derivations, and tabular presentation. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used in the computer processing of the encoded data.

Analytical Schemes

In the analysis of the data, various procedures will be employed per the objectives of the study.

Objective No. 1 which aimed to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of the following variables: age, sex, and track, the descriptive analytical scheme was used.

Objective No. 2 which aimed to determine the extent of teaching competence of secondary school teachers as assessed by the students in the following areas: instructional delivery, classroom management, and assessment delivery, the descriptive analytical scheme was used.

Objective No. 3 which aimed to determine the extent of teaching competence of secondary school teachers as assessed by the students and when they are grouped according to the aforementioned variables, the descriptive analytical scheme was used.

Objective No. 4 which aimed to determine the level of student academic performance of senior high school teachers as assessed by the students and when they were grouped according to the aforementioned variables, the descriptive analytical scheme was used.

Objective No. 5 which aimed to determine the significant difference in the extent of teaching competence of secondary school teachers as assessed by the students and when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables, the comparative analytical scheme was used.

Objective No. 6 which aimed to determine the significant difference in the level of students' academic performance when they are grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables, the comparative analytical scheme was used.

Objective No. 7 which aimed to determine the relationship between the extent of teaching competence and the level of students' academic performance, the relational analytical scheme was used.

Statistical Tools

In the analysis of the data, various statistical tools will be employed per the objectives of the study.

Objective No. 1 which aimed to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of the following variables: age, sex and track, frequency count, and percentage was used. This approach is suitable for establishing the typical characteristics of the study's respondent group.

Categorical data are best described by counting how many of the subjects' responses fall within each category in a frequency distribution and by calculating their percentages or proportions, that is the number of times each response was given by the total number (Mellinger and Hanson, 2017).

Objective No. 2 which aimed to determine the extent of teaching competence of secondary school teachers as assessed by the students in the following areas: instructional delivery, classroom management, and assessment delivery, mean was used.

The mean, often referred to as the average, is a widely used statistic for summarizing a dataset by calculating the sum of all values divided by the number of observations (Gravetter and Wallnau, 2017).

The mean scores were interpreted as follows:

Mean Range	Score Description	Verbal Interpretation
4.50 - 5.00	Always	Very Great Extent
3.50 - 4.49	Oftentimes	Great Extent
2.50 - 3.49	Frequent	Moderate Extent
1.50 - 2.49	Sometimes	Low Extent
1.00 - 1.49	Almost never	Very Low Extent

Objective No. 3 which aimed to determine the extent of teaching competence of secondary school teachers as assessed by the students and when they are grouped according to the aforementioned variables, mean was used.

Objective No. 4 which aimed to determine the level of students' academic performance of senior high school teachers as assessed by the students and when they are grouped according to the aforementioned variables, mean was used.

The mean scores were interpreted as follows based on the DepEd Standard on Learning Progress and Achievement Report:

Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
90 - 100%	Outstanding
85 - 89%	Very Satisfactory
80 - 84%	Satisfactory
75 - 79%	Fairly Satisfactory
74% and below	Did not meet the expectation

Objective No. 5 which aimed to determine the significant difference in the extent of teaching competence of secondary school teachers as assessed by the students and

when grouped and compared according to age and sex, the Mann-Whitney U test was used and for the variable track, Kruskal Wallis H test was used.

The Mann-Whitney U test is particularly useful when the data is ordinal (ranked data) or when the assumptions of normality (normal distribution) for the t-test are not met (Ferguson, 2016)

The Kruskal-Wallis H test, also known as the “one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) on ranks”, is a non-parametric statistical test based on ranks. It is used to assess whether statistically significant differences exist among two or more independent groups in a continuous or ordinal dependent variable.

Objective No. 6 which aimed to determine the significant difference in the level of students’ academic performance when they are grouped and compared according to age and sex, Mann-Whitney U test was used and for the variable track, Kruskal Wallis H test was used.

Objective No. 7 which aimed to determine the significant relationship between the extent of teaching competence and the level of students’ academic performance, Spearman Rho was used.

Spearman's rank-order correlation, often denoted by the Greek letter rho (ρ) or r_s , is a non-parametric alternative to the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (Pallant, 2016). It measures the strength and direction of association between two ranked variables.

In Spearman's rank-order correlation, the null hypothesis states that there is no monotonic association between the ranks of the two variables. This means that a change in the rank of one variable does not necessarily correspond to a change (increase or decrease) in the rank of the other variable.

Finally, the computation of the p-values was interpreted using the following guide. Reject null hypothesis if the p-value is equal to or less than 0.05 level of significance. Accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than 0.05 level of significance

RESULTS

Table 2
Profile of the Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age	younger (below 18 years old)	123	48.2
	older (18 years old and above)	132	51.8

2573

		Total	255	100.00
Sex	male		101	39.6
	female		154	60.4
		Total	269	100.00
Track	GAS		28	11.0
	HUMSS		79	31.0
	ABM		36	14.1
	STEM		20	7.8
	TVL		67	26.3
	Arts & Design		14	5.5
	Sports		11	4.3
		Total	255	100.00

Table 2 shows the profile of the respondents. In terms of age, 123, or 48.2% were younger (below 18 years old) and 132, or 51.8% were older (18 years and above) respondents. In terms of sex, 101, or 39.6% were male, and 154, or 60.4 were female respondents. In terms of track, 28, or 11.0% belonged to GAS, 79 or 31.0% belonged to HUMSS, 36, or 14.1% belonged to STEM, 67, or 26.3% belonged to TVL, 14, or 5.5% belonged to Arts, and Design, and 11 or 4.3% belonged to Sports.

Table 3
Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Instructional Delivery

	Items	Mean	Interpretation
1	Lesson contents are delivered with corresponding visual aids or video clips.	3.90	Great Extent
2	Teachers always ask students if they have questions before proceeding to the next topic.	4.68	Very Great Extent
3	One day before discussing the topic, the teacher assigns students to read in advance - at home or the library.	3.75	Great Extent
4	The teacher always encourages students to throw more questions to clarify some unclear points.	4.14	Great Extent
5	Sometimes, our teacher employs group dynamics in the class for us to understand better the lessons she delivers.	3.93	Great Extent
6	The teacher can manage to provide anecdotes to ease tension and boredom.	3.83	Great Extent
7	In general, the teacher is very effective in delivering lesson content	4.26	Great Extent
8	Even if some of the class projects are done in groups, our teacher manages to make sure that everyone is participating.	4.42	Great Extent

9	Compliments are always given to those who volunteer to provide good answers during class discussions.	4.03	Great Extent
10	Our teacher knows how to empower her students by delegating some tasks to them.	4.10	Great Extent
Overall Mean		4.10	Great Extent

Legend	Mean Range	Score Description	Verbal Interpretation
	4.50 - 5.00	Always	Very Great Extent
	3.50 - 4.49	Oftentimes	Great Extent
	2.50 - 3.49	Frequent	Moderate Extent
	1.50 - 2.49	Sometimes	Low Extent
	1.00 - 1.49	Almost never	Very Low Extent

Table 3 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of instructional delivery. Item No. 2 which states, "Teacher always ask students if they have questions before proceeding to the next topic" got the highest mean score of 4.68, interpreted as "very great extent". Meanwhile, Item No. 3 which states "One day before discussing the topic, the teacher assigns students to read in advance - at home or the library" got the lowest mean score of 3.75, interpreted as "great extent". The overall mean score was 4.10, interpreted as a great extent.

Table 4
Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Classroom Management

Items		Mean	Interpretation
1	The room is very conducive to learning.	4.25	Great Extent
2	Our classroom has a homey atmosphere – curtains, tables, etc.	4.36	Great Extent
3	The cleanliness of the classroom is properly maintained	4.36	Great Extent
4	Noisy students are being called out during class	3.60	Great Extent
5	Blackboards, bulletin boards, and the teachers' tables and chairs are always clean and in place	4.31	Great Extent
6	We have a clean CR inside the classroom	2.21	Low Extent
7	Soap, tissue paper, and others are available inside our classroom toilet	1.96	Low Extent
8	The room is maintained clean every day, floor and walls are dusted.	4.07	Great Extent
9	We have a storage cabinet for our raincoats, umbrellas, or boots during the rainy season.	1.97	Low Extent
10	The room has a clean trash bin	3.66	Great Extent
Overall Mean		3.48	Moderate Extent

Legend	Mean Range	Score Description	Verbal Interpretation
	4.50 - 5.00	Always	Very Great Extent

3.50 - 4.49	Oftentimes	Great Extent
2.50 - 3.49	Frequent	Moderate Extent
1.50 - 2.49	Sometimes	Low Extent
1.00 - 1.49	Almost never	Very Low Extent

Table 4 shows the extent of the teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of classroom management. Item Nos. 2 and 3 which state, “Our classroom has a homey atmosphere – curtains, tables, etc.” and “Cleanliness of the classroom is properly maintained” got the highest mean score of 4.36, interpreted as “great extent”. Meanwhile, Item No. 7 which states, “Soap, tissue papers and others are available inside our classroom toilet” got the lowest mean score of 1.96, interpreted as “low extent”. The overall mean score was 3.48, interpreted as “moderate extent”.

Table 5
Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Assessment Delivery

	Items	Mean	Interpretation
1	Short and long quizzes are consistently given after each lesson	4.05	Great Extent
2	Pointers are provided before the exams	4.42	Great Extent
3	The results of our tests are being discussed with us individually	3.74	Great Extent
4	Exams and long quizzes are being discussed in the class.	4.24	Great Extent
5	Students who score low on long quizzes and exams are being called to be given coaching sessions.	3.54	Great Extent
6	If students are unable to take a test, makeup tests are given	3.91	Great Extent
7	The teacher always asks what part of the exam is difficult.	4.23	Great Extent
8	The teacher maintains total silence during exam days.	4.52	Very Great Extent
9	The students are given the option to tell the teacher what test type they like.	2.96	Moderate Extent
10	Everything that comes out of the exams is from our daily lessons	4.36	Great Extent
	Overall Mean	4.00	Great Extent

Legend	Mean Range	Score Description	Verbal Interpretation
	4.50 - 5.00	Always	Very Great Extent
	3.50 - 4.49	Oftentimes	Great Extent
	2.50 - 3.49	Frequent	Moderate Extent
	1.50 - 2.49	Sometimes	Low Extent
	1.00 - 1.49	Almost never	Very Low Extent

Table 5 shows the extent of the teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of assessment delivery. Item No. 8 which states, “The teacher maintains total silence during exam days” got the highest mean score of 4.52, interpreted as “very great extent”. Meanwhile, Item No. 9 which states, “The students are given the option to tell the teacher what test type they like” got the lowest mean score of 2.96, interpreted as “moderate extent”. The overall mean score was 4.00, interpreted as “great extent”.

Table 6
Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Instructional Delivery According to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1 Lesson contents are delivered with corresponding visual aids or video clips.	3.88	Great Extent	3.92	Great Extent
2 Teachers always ask students if they have questions before proceeding to the next topic.	4.67	Very Great Extent	4.69	Very Great Extent
3 One day before discussing the topic, the teacher assigns students to read in advance - at home or the library.	3.55	Great Extent	3.94	Great Extent
4 The teacher always encourages students to throw more questions to clarify some unclear points.	4.01	Great Extent	4.27	Great Extent
5 Sometimes, our teacher employs group dynamics in the class for us to understand better the lessons she delivers.	3.80	Great Extent	4.05	Great Extent
6 The teacher can manage to provide anecdotes to ease tension and boredom.	3.74	Great Extent	3.91	Great Extent
7 In general, the teacher is very effective in delivering lesson content	4.25	Great Extent	4.27	Great Extent
8 Even if some of the class projects are done in groups, our teacher manages to make sure that everyone is participating.	4.38	Great Extent	4.46	Great Extent
9 Compliments are always given to those who volunteer to provide good answers during class discussions.	3.97	Great Extent	4.08	Great Extent

10	Our teacher knows how to empower her students by delegating some tasks to them.	4.05	Great Extent	4.14	Great Extent
	Overall Mean	4.03	Great Extent	4.17	Great Extent

Legend	Mean Range	Score Description	Verbal Interpretation
	4.50 - 5.00	Always	Very Great Extent
	3.50 - 4.49	Oftentimes	Great Extent
	2.50 - 3.49	Frequent	Moderate Extent
	1.50 - 2.49	Sometimes	Low Extent
	1.00 - 1.49	Almost never	Very Low Extent

Table 6 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of instructional delivery according to age. Item No. 2 which states, "Teacher always ask students if they have questions before proceeding to the next topic" got the highest mean score of 4.67 for younger respondents and 4.69 for older respondents, both were interpreted as "very great extent". Meanwhile, Item No. 3 which states, "One day before discussing the topic, the teacher assigns students to read in advance - at home or the library" got the lowest mean score of 3.55 for younger respondents interpreted it as "great extent", while Item No. 6 which states, "the teacher can manage to provide anecdotes to ease tension and boredom" got the lowest mean score of 3.91 for older respondents interpreted as "great extent". The overall mean scores were 4.03 for younger and 4.17 for older respondents, both were interpreted as "great extent".

Table 7
Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Instructional Delivery According to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1 Lesson contents are delivered with corresponding visual aids or video clips.	3.78	Great Extent	3.97	Great Extent
2 Teachers always ask students if they have questions before proceeding to the next topic.	4.63	Very Great Extent	4.71	Very Great Extent
3 One day before discussing the topic, the teacher assigns students to read in advance - at home or the library.	3.75	Great Extent	3.75	Great Extent
4 The teacher always encourages students to throw more questions to clarify some unclear points.	4.06	Great Extent	4.19	Great Extent

5	Sometimes, our teacher employs group dynamics in the class for us to understand better the lessons she delivers.	3.89	Great Extent	3.95	Great Extent
6	The teacher can manage to provide anecdotes to ease tension and boredom.	3.71	Great Extent	3.90	Great Extent
7	In general, the teacher is very effective in delivering lesson content	4.19	Great Extent	4.31	Great Extent
8	Even if some of the class projects are done in groups, our teacher manages to make sure that everyone is participating.	4.46	Great Extent	4.40	Great Extent
9	Compliments are always given to those who volunteer to provide good answers during class discussions.	4.06	Great Extent	4.01	Great Extent
10	Our teacher knows how to empower her students by delegating some tasks to them.	4.08	Great Extent	4.11	Great Extent
Overall Mean		4.06	Great Extent	4.13	Great Extent

Legend	Mean Range	Score Description	Verbal Interpretation
	4.50 - 5.00	Always	Very Great Extent
	3.50 - 4.49	Oftentimes	Great Extent
	2.50 - 3.49	Frequent	Moderate Extent
	1.50 - 2.49	Sometimes	Low Extent
	1.00 - 1.49	Almost never	Very Low Extent

Table 7 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of instructional delivery according to sex. Item No. 2 which states, "Teacher always ask students if they have questions before" got the highest mean score of 4.63 for male respondents and 4.71 for female respondents, both were interpreted as "very great extent". Meanwhile, Item No. 6 which states, "the teacher can manage to provide anecdotes to ease tension and boredom" got the lowest mean score of 3.71 for male respondents, interpreted as "great extent", while Item No. 3 which states, "One day before discussing the topic, the teacher assigns students to read in advance - at home or the library" got the lowest mean score of 3.75 for male respondents were both interpreted as "great extent", while Item No. 3 which states, "One day before discussing the topic, the teacher assigns students to read in advance - at home or the library" got the lowest mean score of 3.75 for female respondents interpreted as "great extent". The overall mean scores were 4.06 for male and 4.13 for female respondents, both were interpreted as "great extent".

Table 8

Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Instructional Delivery According to GAS and HUMSS

	Items	GAS		HUMSS	
		Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1	Lesson contents are delivered with corresponding visual aids or video clips.	3.82	Great Extent	3.86	Great Extent
2	Teachers always ask students if they have questions before proceeding to the next topic.	4.89	Very Great Extent	4.70	Very Great Extent
3	One day before discussing the topic, the teacher assigns students to read in advance - at home or the library.	3.64	Great Extent	3.85	Great Extent
4	The teacher always encourages students to throw more questions to clarify some unclear points.	4.00	Great Extent	4.11	Great Extent
5	Sometimes, our teacher employs group dynamics in the class for us to understand better the lessons she delivers.	3.79	Great Extent	4.05	Great Extent
6	The teacher can manage to provide anecdotes to ease tension and boredom.	3.61	Great Extent	3.89	Great Extent
7	In general, the teacher is very effective in delivering lesson content	4.07	Great Extent	4.39	Great Extent
8	Even if some of the class projects are done in groups, our teacher manages to make sure that everyone is participating.	4.32	Great Extent	4.54	Great Extent
9	Compliments are always given to those who volunteer to provide good answers during class discussions.	4.14	Great Extent	4.04	Great Extent
10	Our teacher knows how to empower her students by delegating some tasks to them.	4.14	Great Extent	4.19	Great Extent
	Overall Mean	4.04	Great Extent	4.16	Great Extent

Legend	Mean Range	Score Description	Verbal Interpretation
	4.50 - 5.00	Always	Very Great Extent
	3.50 - 4.49	Oftentimes	Great Extent
	2.50 - 3.49	Frequent	Moderate Extent

1.50 - 2.49	Sometimes	Low Extent
1.00 - 1.49	Almost never	Very Low Extent

Table 8 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of instructional delivery according to GAS and HUMSS. Item No. 2 which states, “Teacher always ask students if they have questions before proceeding to the next topic” got the highest mean score of 4.89 for GAS and 4.70 for HUMSS respondents, both were interpreted as “very great extent”. Meanwhile, Item No. 6 which states “The teacher can manage to provide anecdotes to ease tension and boredom” got the lowest mean score of 3.61 for the GAS group, interpreted as “great extent”, while Item No. 3 which states, “One day before discussing the topic, the teacher assigns students to read in advance - at home or the library” got the lowest score of 3.85 for HUMSS group, interpreted as “great extent”. The overall mean scores were 4.04 for the GAS group and 4.16 for the HUMSS group, both were interpreted as “great extent”.

Table 9
Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Instructional Delivery According to ABM and STEM

Items	ABM		STEM	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1 Lesson contents are delivered with corresponding visual aids or video clips.	3.97	Great Extent	3.75	Great Extent
2 Teachers always ask students if they have questions before proceeding to the next topic.	4.69	Very Great Extent	4.45	Great Extent
3 One day before discussing the topic, the teacher assigns students to read in advance - at home or the library.	3.86	Great Extent	3.50	Great Extent
4 The teacher always encourages students to throw more questions to clarify some unclear points.	4.22	Great Extent	4.30	Great Extent
5 Sometimes, our teacher employs group dynamics in the class for us to understand better the lessons she delivers.	3.89	Great Extent	3.65	Great Extent
6 The teacher can manage to provide anecdotes to ease tension and boredom.	3.83	Great Extent	3.65	Great Extent
7 In general, the teacher is very effective in delivering lesson content	4.17	Great Extent	4.40	Great Extent

8	Even if some of the class projects are done in groups, our teacher manages to make sure that everyone is participating.	4.42	Great Extent	4.20	Great Extent
9	Compliments are always given to those who volunteer to provide good answers during class discussions.	4.22	Great Extent	3.95	Great Extent
10	Our teacher knows how to empower her students by delegating some tasks to them.	4.08	Great Extent	3.90	Great Extent
Overall Mean		4.14	Great Extent	3.98	Great Extent

Legend	Mean Range	Score Description	Verbal Interpretation
	4.50 - 5.00	Always	Very Great Extent
	3.50 - 4.49	Oftentimes	Great Extent
	2.50 - 3.49	Frequent	Moderate Extent
	1.50 - 2.49	Sometimes	Low Extent
	1.00 - 1.49	Almost never	Very Low Extent

Table 9 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of instructional delivery according to ABM and STEM. Item No. 2 which states, "Teacher always ask students if they have questions before proceeding to the next topic" got the highest mean score of 4.69 for ABM, interpreted as "great extent" and 4.45 for STEM respondents, interpreted as "great extent". Meanwhile, Item No. 6 which states "The teacher can manage to provide anecdotes to ease tension and boredom" got the lowest mean score of 3.83 for ABM, interpreted as "great extent", while Item No. 3 which states, "One day before discussing the topic, the teacher assigns students to read in advance - at home or the library" got the lowest 3.50 for STEM, interpreted as "great extent". The overall mean scores were 4.14 for the ABM group and 3.98 for the STEM group, both were interpreted as "great extent".

Table 10
Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Instructional Delivery According to TVL, Arts & Design, and Sports

Items	TVL		Arts & Design		Sports	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1 Lesson contents are delivered with corresponding visual aids or video clips.	4.19	Great Extent	3.36	Moderate Extent	3.27	Moderate Extent

2	Teachers always ask students if they have questions before proceeding to the next topic.	4.66	Very Great Extent	4.64	Very Great Extent	4.64	Very Great Extent
3	One day before discussing the topic, the teacher assigns students to read in advance - at home or the library.	3.91	Great Extent	3.79	Great Extent	2.45	Low Extent
4	The teacher always encourages students to throw more questions to clarify some unclear points.	4.16	Great Extent	4.14	Great Extent	4.00	Great Extent
5	Sometimes, our teacher employs group dynamics in the class for us to understand better the lessons she delivers.	3.97	Great Extent	4.00	Great Extent	3.73	Great Extent
6	The teacher can manage to provide anecdotes to ease tension and boredom.	4.01	Great Extent	3.64	Great Extent	3.36	Moderate Extent
7	In general, the teacher is very effective in delivering lesson content	4.37	Great Extent	4.07	Great Extent	3.36	Great Extent
8	Even if some of the class projects are done in groups, our teacher manages to make sure that	4.52	Very Great Extent	4.43	Great Extent	3.64	Great Extent

9	everyone is participating. Compliments are always given to those who volunteer to provide good answers during class discussions.	3.96	Great Extent	4.00	Great Extent	3.64	Great Extent
10	Our teacher knows how to empower her students by delegating some tasks to them.	4.19	Great Extent	4.21	Great Extent	3.00	Moderate Extent
	Overall Mean	4.20	Great Extent	4.03	Great Extent	3.51	Great Extent

Legend	Mean Range	Score Description	Verbal Interpretation
	4.50 - 5.00	Always	Very Great Extent
	3.50 - 4.49	Oftentimes	Great Extent
	2.50 - 3.49	Frequent	Moderate Extent
	1.50 - 2.49	Sometimes	Low Extent
	1.00 - 1.49	Almost never	Very Low Extent

Table 10 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of instructional delivery according to TVL, Arts & Design, and Sports. Item No. 2 which states. "Teacher always asks students if they have questions before proceeding to the next topic" got the highest mean score of 4.66 for the TVL group and 4.64 for both the Arts & Design and Sports group, all were interpreted as "very great extent". Meanwhile. Item No. 3 which states, "One day before discussing the topic, the teacher assigns students to read in advance - at home or the library" got the lowest 3.91 for the TVL group, interpreted as "great extent" and 2.45 for the Sports group, interpreted as "low extent", while Item No. 1 which states, "Lesson contents are delivered with corresponding visual aids or video clips" got the lowest mean score of 3.36 for Arts & Design group, interpreted as "moderate extent. The overall mean scores were 4.20 for TVL, 4.03 for Arts and Design, and 3.51 for Sports group, all were interpreted as "great extent".

Table 11

Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Classroom Management According to Age

	Items	Younger		Older	
		Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1	The room is very conducive to learning.	4.27	Great Extent	4.24	Great Extent
2	Our classroom has a homey atmosphere – curtains, tables, etc.	4.42	Great Extent	4.30	Great Extent
3	The cleanliness of the classroom is properly maintained	4.33	Great Extent	4.39	Great Extent
4	Noisy students are being called out during class	3.59	Great Extent	3.61	Great Extent
5	Blackboards, bulletin boards, and the teachers' tables and chairs are always clean and in place	4.33	Great Extent	4.30	Great Extent
6	We have a clean CR inside the classroom	2.02	Low Extent	2.38	Low Extent
7	Soap, tissue paper, and others are available inside our classroom toilet	1.87	Low Extent	2.08	Low Extent
8	The room is maintained clean every day, floor and walls are dusted.	3.93	Great Extent	4.19	Great Extent
9	We have a storage cabinet for our raincoats, umbrellas, or boots during the rainy season.	1.73	Low Extent	2.19	Low Extent
10	The room has a clean trash bin	3.64	Great Extent	3.68	Great Extent
	Overall Mean	3.41	Moderate Extent	3.54	Great Extent

Legend	Mean Range	Score Description	Verbal Interpretation
	4.50 - 5.00	Always	Very Great Extent
	3.50 - 4.49	Oftentimes	Great Extent
	2.50 - 3.49	Frequent	Moderate Extent
	1.50 - 2.49	Sometimes	Low Extent
	1.00 - 1.49	Almost never	Very Low Extent

Table 11 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of classroom management according to age. Item No. 2 which states, "Our classroom has a homey atmosphere – curtains, tables, etc." got the highest mean score of 4.42 for the younger group, interpreted as "great extent", while Item No. 3 which states, "Cleanliness of the classroom is properly maintained" got the highest mean score of 4.39 for the older group, interpreted as "great extent". Meanwhile,

Item No. 9 which states, “We have a storage cabinet for our raincoats, umbrellas or boots during the rainy season” got the lowest mean score of 1.73 for the younger group, interpreted as “low extent”, while Item No. 7 which states, “Soap, tissue papers, and others are available inside our classroom toilet” got the lowest mean score of 2.08 for the older group, interpreted as “low extent”. The overall mean scores were 3.41 for the younger group, interpreted as “moderate extent” and 3.54 for the older group, interpreted as “great extent”.

Table 12
Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Classroom Management According to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1 The room is very conducive to learning.	4.29	Great Extent	4.23	Great Extent
2 Our classroom has a homey atmosphere – curtains, tables, etc.	4.30	Great Extent	4.40	Great Extent
3 The cleanliness of the classroom is properly maintained	4.31	Great Extent	4.40	Great Extent
4 Noisy students are being called out during class	3.77	Great Extent	3.49	Moderate Extent
5 Blackboards, bulletin boards, and the teachers’ tables and chairs are always clean and in place	4.26	Great Extent	4.34	Great Extent
6 We have a clean CR inside the classroom	2.31	Low Extent	2.14	Low Extent
7 Soap, tissue paper, and others are available inside our classroom toilet	2.02	Low Extent	1.95	Low Extent
8 The room is maintained clean every day, floor and walls are dusted.	4.03	Great Extent	4.09	Great Extent
9 We have a storage cabinet for our raincoats, umbrellas, or boots during the rainy season.	2.12	Low Extent	1.87	Low Extent
10 The room has a clean trash bin	3.61	Great Extent	3.69	Great Extent
Overall Mean	3.50	Great Extent	3.46	Great Extent

Legend	Mean Range	Score Description	Verbal Interpretation
	4.50 - 5.00	Always	Very Great Extent
	3.50 - 4.49	Oftentimes	Great Extent
	2.50 - 3.49	Frequent	Moderate Extent

1.50 - 2.49	Sometimes	Low Extent
1.00 - 1.49	Almost never	Very Low Extent

Table 12 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of classroom management according to sex. Item No. 3 which states, “Cleanliness of the classroom is properly maintained” got the highest mean score of 4.31 for the male group, interpreted as “great extent”, while Items No. 2 and 3 which states, “Our classroom has a homey atmosphere – curtains, tables, etc.” and “Cleanliness of the classroom is properly maintained” got the highest mean score of 4.40 for the female group, interpreted as “great extent”. Meanwhile, Item No. 7 which states, “Soap, tissue papers, and others are available inside our classroom toilet” got the lowest mean score of 2.02 for the male group, interpreted as “low extent”, while Item No. 9 which states, “We have a storage cabinet for our raincoats, umbrellas or boots during the rainy season” got the lowest mean score of 1.87 for the female group, interpreted as “low extent”. The overall mean scores were 3.50 for the male group, interpreted as “great extent” and 3.46 for the female group, interpreted as “moderate extent”.

Table 13
Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Classroom Management According to GAS and HUMSS

Items	GAS		HUMSS	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1 The room is very conducive to learning.	4.14	Great Extent	4.25	Great Extent
2 Our classroom has a homey atmosphere – curtains, tables, etc.	4.18	Great Extent	4.46	Great Extent
3 The cleanliness of the classroom is properly maintained	4.25	Great Extent	4.38	Great Extent
4 Noisy students are being called out during class	4.14	Great Extent	3.56	Great Extent
5 Blackboards, bulletin boards, and the teachers’ tables and chairs are always clean and in place	4.29	Great Extent	4.37	Great Extent
6 We have a clean CR inside the classroom	2.07	Low Extent	2.13	Low Extent
7 Soap, tissue paper, and others are available inside our classroom toilet	1.75	Low Extent	1.87	Low Extent
8 The room is maintained clean every day, floor and walls are dusted.	4.00	Great Extent	4.16	Great Extent

9	We have a storage cabinet for our raincoats, umbrellas, or boots during the rainy season.	1.86	Low Extent	1.53	Low Extent
10	The room has a clean trash bin	3.57	Great Extent	3.49	Moderate Extent
Overall Mean		3.43	Moderate Extent	3.42	Moderate Extent

Legend	Mean Range	Score Description	Verbal Interpretation
	4.50 - 5.00	Always	Very Great Extent
	3.50 - 4.49	Oftentimes	Great Extent
	2.50 - 3.49	Frequent	Moderate Extent
	1.50 - 2.49	Sometimes	Low Extent
	1.00 - 1.49	Almost never	Very Low Extent

Table 13 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of classroom management according to GAS and HUMSS. Item No. 5 which states, “Blackboards, bulletin boards, and the teachers’ table and chair are always clean and in place” got the highest mean score of 4.29 for the GAS group, interpreted as “great extent”, while Item No. 2 which states, “Our classroom has a homey atmosphere – curtains, tables, etc.” got the highest mean score of 4.46 for HUMSS, interpreted as “great extent”. Meanwhile, Item No. 7 which states, “Soap, tissue papers, and others are available inside our classroom toilet” got the lowest mean score of 1.75 for the GAS group, interpreted as “low extent”, while Item No. 9 which states, “We have a storage cabinet for our raincoats, umbrellas or boots during the rainy season” got the lowest mean score of 1.53 for HUMSS group, interpreted as “low extent”. The overall mean scores were 3.43 for GAS and 3.42 for the HUMSS group, both were interpreted as “moderate extent”.

Table 14
Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Classroom Management According to ABM and STEM

Items	ABM		STEM	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1 The room is very conducive to learning.	4.03	Great Extent	4.20	Great Extent
2 Our classroom has a homey atmosphere – curtains, tables, etc.	4.22	Great Extent	4.60	Very Great Extent
3 The cleanliness of the classroom is properly maintained	4.44	Great Extent	4.05	Great Extent
4 Noisy students are being called out during class	4.03	Great Extent	3.10	Moderate Extent

5	Blackboards, bulletin boards, and the teachers' tables and chairs are always clean and in place	4.08	Great Extent	4.30	Great Extent
6	We have a clean CR inside the classroom	2.25	Low Extent	3.30	Moderate Extent
7	Soap, tissue paper, and others are available inside our classroom toilet	2.00	Low Extent	2.50	Moderate Extent
8	The room is maintained clean every day, floor and walls are dusted.	3.97	Great Extent	4.10	Great Extent
9	We have a storage cabinet for our raincoats, umbrellas, or boots during the rainy season.	2.22	Low Extent	2.85	Moderate Extent
10	The room has a clean trash bin	3.58	Great Extent	3.85	Great Extent
Overall Mean		3.48	Moderate Extent	3.69	Great Extent

Legend	Mean Range	Score Description	Verbal Interpretation
	4.50 - 5.00	Always	Very Great Extent
	3.50 - 4.49	Oftentimes	Great Extent
	2.50 - 3.49	Frequent	Moderate Extent
	1.50 - 2.49	Sometimes	Low Extent
	1.00 - 1.49	Almost never	Very Low Extent

Table 14 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of classroom management according to ABM and STEM. Item No. 3 which states, "Cleanliness of the classroom is properly maintained" got the highest mean score of 4.44 for the ABM group, interpreted as "great extent", while Item No 2 which states, "Our classroom has a homey atmosphere - curtains, tables, etc." got the highest mean score of 4.60 for STEM, interpreted as "great extent". Meanwhile, Item No. 7 which states, "Soap, tissue papers, and others are available inside our classroom toilet" got the lowest mean score of 2.00 for the ABM group, interpreted as "low extent" and 2.50 for the STEM group, interpreted as "moderate extent". The overall mean scores were 3.48 for ABM, interpreted as "moderate extent" and 3.69 for the STEM group, interpreted as "great extent".

Table 15

Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Classroom Management According to TVL, Arts & Design, and Sports

Items	TVL		Arts & Design		Sports	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1 The room is very conducive to learning.	4.48	Great Extent	4.36	Great Extent	3.91	Great Extent
2 Our classroom has a homey atmosphere – curtains, tables, etc.	4.46	Great Extent	4.57	Very Great Extent	3.27	Moderate Extent
3 The cleanliness of the classroom is properly maintained	4.42	Great Extent	4.64	Very Great Extent	4.18	Great Extent
4 Noisy students are being called out during class	3.51	Great Extent	3.50	Great Extent	2.82	Moderate Extent
5 Blackboards, bulletin boards, and the teachers' tables and chairs are always clean and in place	4.40	Great Extent	4.21	Great Extent	4.27	Great Extent
6 We have a clean CR inside the classroom	2.09	Low Extent	1.93	Low Extent	2.09	Low Extent
7 Soap, tissue paper, and others are available inside our classroom toilet	2.01	Low Extent	1.50	Low Extent	2.73	Moderate Extent
8 The room is maintained clean every day, floor and walls are dusted.	4.09	Great Extent	4.29	Great Extent	3.36	Moderate Extent
9 We have a storage cabinet for our raincoats, umbrellas, or	1.73	Low Extent	2.43	Low Extent	3.82	Great Extent

10	boots during the rainy season. The room has a clean trash bin	4.03	Great Extent	3.43	Moderate Extent	3.09	Moderate Extent
	Overall Mean	3.52	Great Extent	3.49	Moderate Extent	3.35	Moderate Extent

Legend	Mean Range	Score Description	Verbal Interpretation
	4.50 - 5.00	Always	Very Great Extent
	3.50 - 4.49	Oftentimes	Great Extent
	2.50 - 3.49	Frequent	Moderate Extent
	1.50 - 2.49	Sometimes	Low Extent
	1.00 - 1.49	Almost never	Very Low Extent

Table 15 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of classroom management according to TVL, Arts & Design, and Sports. Item No. 1 which states, “The room is very conducive for learning” got the highest mean score of 4.48 for the TVL group, interpreted as “great extent”, while Item No 3 which states, “Cleanliness of the classroom is properly maintained” got the highest mean score of 4.64 for Arts & Design group, interpreted as “very great extent” and Item No. 5 which states, “Blackboards, bulletin boards, and the teachers’ table and chair are always clean and in place” got the highest mean score of 4.27 for Sports group, interpreted as “great extent”. Meanwhile, Item No. 9 which states, “We have a storage cabinet for our raincoats, umbrellas or boots during the rainy season” got the lowest mean score of 1.73 for the TVL group, interpreted as “low extent”; Item No. 7 which states, “Soap, tissue papers, and others are available inside our classroom toilet” got the lowest mean score of 1.50 for Arts & Design group, interpreted as “low extent” and Item No. 6 which states, “We have a clean CR inside the classroom” 2.09 for Sport group, interpreted as “low extent”. The overall mean scores were 3.52 for TVL, interpreted as “great extent”, while 3.49 for the Arts & Design group and 3.35 for the Sports group, both were interpreted as “moderate extent”.

Table 16
Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Assessment Delivery According to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1 Short and long quizzes are consistently given after each lesson	4.03	Great Extent	4.07	Great Extent
2 Pointers are provided before the exams	4.41	Great Extent	4.42	Great Extent
3 The results of our tests are being discussed with us individually	3.61	Great Extent	3.86	Great Extent

4	Exams and long quizzes are being discussed in the class.	4.19	Great Extent	4.30	Great Extent
5	Students who score low on long quizzes and exams are being called to be given coaching sessions.	3.41	Moderate Extent	3.65	Great Extent
6	If students are unable to take a test, makeup tests are given	3.76	Great Extent	4.06	Great Extent
7	The teacher always asks what part of the exam is difficult.	4.25	Great Extent	4.21	Great Extent
8	The teacher maintains total silence during exam days.	4.45	Great Extent	4.58	Very Great Extent
9	The students are given the option to tell the teacher what test type they like.	2.76	Moderate Extent	3.14	Moderate Extent
10	Everything that comes out of the exams is from our daily lessons	4.37	Great Extent	4.35	Great Extent
Overall Mean		3.92	Great Extent	4.06	Great Extent

Legend	Mean Range	Score Description	Verbal Interpretation
	4.50 - 5.00	Always	Very Great Extent
	3.50 - 4.49	Oftentimes	Great Extent
	2.50 - 3.49	Frequent	Moderate Extent
	1.50 - 2.49	Sometimes	Low Extent
	1.00 - 1.49	Almost never	Very Low Extent

Table 16 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of assessment delivery according to age. Item No. 8 which states, “The teacher maintains total silence during exam days” got the highest mean score of 4.45 for the younger group, interpreted as “great extent” and 4.58 for the older group, interpreted as “very great extent”. Meanwhile, Item No. 9 which states, “The students are given the option to tell the teacher what test type they like” got the lowest mean score of 2.76 for the younger group and 3.14 for the older group, both were interpreted as “moderate extent”. The overall mean scores were 3.92 for the younger group and 4.06 for the older group, both were interpreted as “great extent”.

Table 17
Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Assessment Delivery According to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1 Short and long quizzes are consistently given after each lesson	3.99	Great Extent	4.09	Great Extent

2	Pointers are provided before the exams	4.49	Great Extent	4.38	Great Extent
3	The results of our tests are being discussed with us individually	3.80	Great Extent	3.69	Great Extent
4	Exams and long quizzes are being discussed in the class.	4.25	Great Extent	4.24	Great Extent
5	Students who score low on long quizzes and exams are being called to be given coaching sessions.	3.68	Great Extent	3.44	Moderate Extent
6	If students are unable to take a test, makeup tests are given	4.01	Great Extent	3.85	Great Extent
7	The teacher always asks what part of the exam is difficult.	4.19	Great Extent	4.26	Great Extent
8	The teacher maintains total silence during exam days.	4.51	Very Great Extent	4.52	Very Great Extent
9	The students are given the option to tell the teacher what test type they like.	3.27	Moderate Extent	2.76	Moderate Extent
10	Everything that comes out of the exams is from our daily lessons	4.40	Great Extent	4.33	Great Extent
Overall Mean		4.06	Great Extent	3.96	Great Extent

Legend	Mean Range	Score Description	Verbal Interpretation
	4.50 - 5.00	Always	Very Great Extent
	3.50 - 4.49	Oftentimes	Great Extent
	2.50 - 3.49	Frequent	Moderate Extent
	1.50 - 2.49	Sometimes	Low Extent
	1.00 - 1.49	Almost never	Very Low Extent

Table 17 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of assessment delivery according to sex. Item No. 8 which states, "The teacher maintains total silence during exam days" got the highest mean score of 4.51 for the male group and 4.52 for the female group, both were interpreted as "very great extent". Meanwhile, Item No. 9 which states, "The students are given the option to tell the teacher what test type they like" got the lowest mean score of 3.27 for the male group and 2.76 for the older group, both were interpreted as "moderate extent". The overall mean scores were 4.06 for the male group and 3.96 for the female group, both were interpreted as "great extent".

Table 18

Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Assessment Delivery According to GAS and HUMSS

	Items	GAS		HUMSS	
		Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1	Short and long quizzes are consistently given after each lesson	4.11	Great Extent	4.05	Great Extent
2	Pointers are provided before the exams	4.61	Very Great Extent	4.51	Very Great Extent
3	The results of our tests are being discussed with us individually	4.21	Great Extent	3.63	Great Extent
4	Exams and long quizzes are being discussed in the class.	4.50	Very Great Extent	4.10	Great Extent
5	Students who score low on long quizzes and exams are being called to be given coaching sessions.	4.04	Great Extent	3.57	Great Extent
6	If students are unable to take a test, makeup tests are given	4.21	Great Extent	3.63	Great Extent
7	The teacher always asks what part of the exam is difficult.	4.32	Great Extent	4.23	Great Extent
8	The teacher maintains total silence during exam days.	4.68	Very Great Extent	4.57	Very Great Extent
9	The students are given the option to tell the teacher what test type they like.	3.18	Moderate Extent	2.87	Moderate Extent
10	Everything that comes out of the exams is from our daily lessons	4.43	Great Extent	4.32	Great Extent
	Overall Mean	4.23	Great Extent	3.95	Great Extent

Legend	Mean Range	Score Description	Verbal Interpretation
	4.50 - 5.00	Always	Very Great Extent
	3.50 - 4.49	Oftentimes	Great Extent
	2.50 - 3.49	Frequent	Moderate Extent
	1.50 - 2.49	Sometimes	Low Extent
	1.00 - 1.49	Almost never	Very Low Extent

Table 18 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of assessment delivery according to GAS and HUMMS. Item No. 8 which states, "The teacher maintains total silence during exam days" got the highest mean score of 4.68 for the GAS group and 4.57 for the HUMSS group, both were interpreted as "very great extent". Meanwhile, Item No. 9 which states, "The students are given the option to tell the teacher what test type they like" got the lowest mean score of 3.18 for the GAS group and 2.87 for the HUMMS group, both were

interpreted as “moderate extent”. The overall mean scores were 4.23 for the GAS group and 3.95 for the HUMSS group, both were interpreted as “great extent”.

Table 19
Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Assessment Delivery According to ABM and STEM

Items	GAS		HUMSS	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1 Short and long quizzes are consistently given after each lesson	4.14	Great Extent	3.80	Great Extent
2 Pointers are provided before the exams	4.31	Great Extent	4.35	Great Extent
3 The results of our tests are being discussed with us individually	3.78	Great Extent	3.15	Great Extent
4 Exams and long quizzes are being discussed in the class.	4.28	Great Extent	4.55	Very Great Extent
5 Students who score low on long quizzes and exams are being called to be given coaching sessions.	3.72	Great Extent	3.55	Great Extent
6 If students are unable to take a test, makeup tests are given	3.97	Great Extent	4.50	Very Great Extent
7 The teacher always asks what part of the exam is difficult.	4.31	Great Extent	4.35	Great Extent
8 The teacher maintains total silence during exam days.	4.39	Great Extent	4.45	Great Extent
9 The students are given the option to tell the teacher what test type they like.	3.33	Moderate Extent	2.65	Moderate Extent
10 Everything that comes out of the exams is from our daily lessons	4.33	Great Extent	4.40	Great Extent
Overall Mean	4.06	Great Extent	3.98	Great Extent

Legend	Mean Range	Score Description	Verbal Interpretation
	4.50 - 5.00	Always	Very Great Extent
	3.50 - 4.49	Oftentimes	Great Extent
	2.50 - 3.49	Frequent	Moderate Extent
	1.50 - 2.49	Sometimes	Low Extent
	1.00 - 1.49	Almost never	Very Low Extent

Table 19 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of assessment delivery according to ABM and STEM. Item No. 8 which states, “The teacher maintains total silence during exam days” got the

highest mean score of 4.39 for the ABM group, interpreted as “great extent”, while Item No. 4 which states, “Exams and long quizzes are being discussed in the class” got the highest mean score of 4.55 for STEM group, interpreted as “very great extent”. Meanwhile, Item No. 9 which states, “The students are given the option to tell the teacher what test type they like” got the lowest mean score of 3.33 for the ABM group and 2.65 for the STEM group, both were interpreted as “moderate extent”. The overall mean scores were 4.06 for the ABM group and 3.98 for the STEM group, both were interpreted as “great extent”.

Table 20
Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Assessment Delivery According to TVL, Arts & Design, and Sports

Items	TVL		Arts & Design		Sports	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1 Short and long quizzes are consistently given after each lesson	4.13	Great Extent	3.93	Great Extent	3.73	Great Extent
2 Pointers are provided before the exams	4.48	Great Extent	4.29	Great Extent	3.64	Great Extent
3 The results of our tests are being discussed with us individually	3.85	Great Extent	3.93	Great Extent	3.27	Great Extent
4 Exams and long quizzes are being discussed in the class.	4.37	Great Extent	3.79	Great Extent	3.82	Great Extent
5 Students who score low on long quizzes and exams are being called to be given coaching sessions.	3.28	Moderate Extent	3.14	Moderate Extent	3.45	Moderate Extent
6 If students are unable to take a test, makeup tests are given	3.85	Great Extent	3.93	Great Extent	4.00	Great Extent
7 The teacher always asks what	4.22	Great Extent	4.07	Great Extent	3.82	Great Extent

	part of the exam is difficult.						
8	The teacher maintains total silence during exam days.	4.60	Very Great Extent	4.36	Great Extent	4.18	Great Extent
9	The students are given the option to tell the teacher what test type they like.	2.91	Moderate Extent	2.64	Moderate Extent	3.09	Moderate Extent
10	Everything that comes out of the exams is from our daily lessons	4.55	Very Great Extent	4.07	Great Extent	3.64	Great Extent
	Overall Mean	4.03	Great Extent	3.81	Great Extent	3.66	Great Extent

Legend	Mean Range	Score Description	Verbal Interpretation
	4.50 - 5.00	Always	Very Great Extent
	3.50 - 4.49	Oftentimes	Great Extent
	2.50 - 3.49	Frequent	Moderate Extent
	1.50 - 2.49	Sometimes	Low Extent
	1.00 - 1.49	Almost never	Very Low Extent

Table 20 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of assessment delivery according to TVL, Arts & Design, and Sports. Item No. 8 which states, “The teacher maintains total silence during exam days” got the highest mean score of 4.60 for the TVL group, interpreted as “very great extent”; 4.36 for Arts & Design and 4.18 for Sports, both were interpreted as “great extent”. Meanwhile, Item No. 9 which states, “The students are given the option to tell the teacher what test type they like” got the lowest mean score of 2.91 for the TVL group, 2.64 for the Arts & Design group, and 3.09 for the Sports group, all were interpreted as “moderate extent”. The overall mean scores were 4.03 for the TVL group, 3.81 for the Arts & Design group, and 3.66 for the Sports group, all were interpreted as “great extent”.

Table 21
Level of Students’ Academic Performance when They Are Grouped According to Variables

Variable	Category	Mean	Interpretation
Age	Younger	86.28	Very Satisfactory
	Older	86.51	Very Satisfactory
Sex	Male	86.81	Very Satisfactory
	Female	86.13	Very Satisfactory

	GAS	87.14	Very Satisfactory
	HUMSS	87.15	Very Satisfactory
	ABM	86.67	Very Satisfactory
Track	STEM	92.30	Outstanding
	TVL	84.22	Satisfactory
	Arts & Design	84.43	Satisfactory
	Sports	83.27	Satisfactory
	Overall Mean	86.45	Very Satisfactory

Legend	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
	90 - 100%	Outstanding
	85 - 89%	Very Satisfactory
	80 - 84%	Satisfactory
	75 - 79%	Fairly Satisfactory
	74% and below	Did not meet the expectation

Table 21 shows the level of students' performance when grouped according to variables. When grouped according to age, the younger group has a mean score of 86.28 and 86.51 for the older group, both were interpreted as "very satisfactory". When grouped according to sex, the male group has a mean score of 86.81 and 86.13 for the female group, both were interpreted as "very satisfactory". When grouped according to track, the STEM group obtained a mean score of 92.30, interpreted as "outstanding" while the Sports group had a mean score of 83.27, interpreted as "satisfactory".

Table 22
Difference in the Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Instructional Delivery When they are Grouped and Compared According to Age, Sex, and Track

Variable	Category	Mean	Mann Whitney U	Kruskal Wallis H	p- value	Sig level	Interpretatio n
Age	Younger	115.01	6520.00		0.006		Significant
	Older	140.11					
Sex	Male	120.66	7036.00		0.197		Not Significant
	Female	132.81					
Track	GAS	118.66		16.43	0.012	0.05	Significant
	HUMSS	136.99					
	ABM	133.51					
	STEM	106.40					
	TVL	139.75					
	Arts & Design	113.18					
Sports	55.77						

Level of significance = 0.05

Table 22 shows the comparative analysis if the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of instructional delivery according to variables. When grouped according to sex, the male group has a mean score of 120.66 and 132.81 for the female group, the computed U-test was 7036.00 and the p-value was 0.197, which is higher than the significance level of 0.05, interpreted as “not significant”.

Table 23

Difference in the Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Classroom Management When they are Grouped and Compared According to Age, Sex, and Track

Variable	Category	Mean	Mann Whitney U	Kruskal Wallis H	p- value	Sig level	Interpretatio n
Age	Younger	118.31	6926.50		0.042		Significant
	Older	137.03					
Sex	Male	132.71	7301.00		0.408		Not Significant
	Female	124.91					
Track	GAS	119.23		6.32	0.388	0.05	Not Significant
	HUMSS	122.97					
	ABM	129.47					
	STEM	160.60					
	TVL	130.20					
	Arts & Design	134.11					
Sports	101.18						

Level of significance = 0.05

Table 23 shows the comparative analysis if the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of classroom management according to variables. When grouped according to sex, the male group has a mean score of 132.71 and 124.91 for the female group, the computed U-test was 7301.00 and the p-value was 0.408, it is higher than the significance level of 0.05, interpreted as “not significant”. When grouped according to track, the GAS group has a mean score of 119.23; 122.97 for HUMMS; 129.47 for ABM; 160.60 for STEM; 130.20 for TVL; 134.11 for Arts & Design, and 101.18 for SPORTS, the computed H-test was 6.32 and the p-value was 0.388, it is higher than the significance level of 0.05, interpreted as “not significant”.

Table 24

Difference in the Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Assessment Delivery When they are Grouped and Compared According to Age, Sex, and Track

Variable	Category	Mean	Mann Whitney U	Kruskal Wallis H	p- value	Sig level	Interpretatio n
Age	Younger	117.19	6788.50		0.024		Significant
	Older	138.07					
Sex	Male	137.51	6816.00		0.095	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	121.76					
	GAS	118.66					
	HUMSS	136.99					
Track	ABM	133.51		12.38	0.054		Not Significant
	STEM	106.40					
	TVL	139.75					
	Arts & Design	113.18					
	Sports	55.77					

Level of significance = 0.05

Table 24 shows the comparative analysis if the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of assessment delivery according to variables. When grouped according to sex, the male group has a mean score of 137.51 and 121.76 for the female group, the computed U-test was 6816.00 and the p-value was 0.095, which is higher than the significance level of 0.05, interpreted as “not significant”. When grouped according to track, the GAS group has a mean score of 118.66; 136.99 for HUMMS; 133.51 for ABM; 106.40 for STEM; 139.75 for TVL; 133.18 for Arts & Design, and 55.77 for Sports, the computed H-test was 12.38 and the p-value was 0.054, it is higher than the significance level of 0.05, interpreted as “not significant”.

Table 25

Differences in the Level of Students’ Academic Performance when they are Grouped and Compared According to Age, Sex, and Track

Variable	Category	Mean	Mann Whitney U	Kruskal Wallis H	p- value	Sig level	Interpretatio n
Age	Younger	125.57	7819.50		0.611	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	130.26					
Sex	Male	135.72	6997.00		0.174		Not Significant
	Female	122.94					

	GAS	143.30			
	HUMSS	141.35			
	ABM	133.69			
Track	STEM	234.08	75.34	0.000	Significant
	TVL	87.93			
	Arts & Design	91.43			
	Sports	72.32			

Level of significance = 0.05

Table 25 shows the comparative analysis of the level of academic performance of senior high school teachers as assessed by students when they are grouped and compared according to variables. When grouped according to age, the younger group has a mean score of 125.57 and 130.26 for the older group, the computed U-test was 7819.50 and the p-value was 0.611, which is higher than the significance level of 0.05, interpreted as “not significant”. When grouped according to sex, the male group has a mean score of 13.72 and 122.94 for the female group, the computed U-test was 6997.00 and the p-value was 0.174, it is higher than the significance level of 0.05, interpreted as “not significant”.

Table 26
Relationship Between the Extent of Teaching Competence and the Level of Students' Academic Performance

Variables	rho	Sig. level	p-value	Interpretation
Extent of Teaching Competence Level of Students' Academic Performance	0.020	0.05	0.756	Not Significant

Level of significance = 0.05

Table 26 shows the relational analysis between the extent of teaching competence and the level of students' academic performance. The extent of teaching competence and the level of student's academic performance has a computed rho-value of 0.020 and a p-value of 0.756, it is higher than the level of significance of 0.05, interpreted as “not significant”.

DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents

Table 2 shows the profile of the respondents. In terms of age, 123, or 48.2% were younger (below 18 years old) and 132, or 51.8% were older (18 years and above) respondents. In terms of sex, 101, or 39.6% were male, and 154, or 60.4 were female respondents. In terms of track, 28, or 11.0% belonged to GAS, 79 or 31.0% belonged to HUMSS, 36, or 14.1% belonged to STEM, 67, or 26.3% belonged to TVL, 14, or 5.5% belonged to Arts, and Design, and 11 or 4.3% belonged to Sports.

The findings of the study showed that the majority of the respondents belong to the younger group. A little over half of the total number of respondents were female. The majority of the respondents came from HUMSS Track.

In surveys, demographics like age, education, and income describe the population being studied (De Franzo, 2015). This information is crucial for crafting an effective survey. It guides who gets surveyed (target population) and how the collected data is analyzed. By segmenting responses based on demographics, researchers can uncover variations in how different groups answer the survey questions, leading to a more nuanced understanding of the results.

Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Instructional Delivery

Table 3 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of instructional delivery.

Item No. 2 which states, "Teacher always ask students if they have questions before proceeding to the next topic" got the highest mean score of 4.68, interpreted as "very great extent". Meanwhile, Item No. 3 which states "One day before discussing the topic, the teacher assigns students to read in advance - at home or the library" got the lowest mean score of 3.75, interpreted as "great extent". The overall mean score was 4.10, interpreted as a great extent.

The findings showed that in terms of instructional delivery, the strength of the teachers lies in the fact that they are able to ask back the learners if there are things that they don't understand before proceeding to another topic. On the other hand, the result of the study showed the inability of some teachers to assign advanced reading materials for the next day's topic.

Sickler (2017) confirmed that students seem to direct the majority of their energy to learning the material after class, which causes an unnecessary cycle of complications. Many fall into the trap of trying to copy down every word during lectures, leading to a frantic struggle to keep up. To break this unproductive cycle, students should prioritize

coming to class prepared. A brief preview of the day's material beforehand can save them hours of ineffective studying later.

Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Classroom Management

Table 4 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of classroom management.

Item Nos. 2 and 3 which state, "Our classroom has a homey atmosphere – curtains, tables, etc." and "Cleanliness of the classroom is properly maintained" got the highest mean score of 4.36, interpreted as "great extent". Meanwhile, Item No. 7 which states, "Soap, tissue papers and others are available inside our classroom toilet" got the lowest mean score of 1.96, interpreted as "low extent". The overall mean score was 3.48, interpreted as "moderate extent".

The study identified strengths and weaknesses in classroom cleanliness. Teachers were praised for creating a clean and welcoming atmosphere in the classrooms. However, a recurring issue was the lack of consistent supplies like soap, toilet paper, and other essentials in the restrooms. This inconsistency between the well-maintained classrooms and potentially unmaintained restrooms could negatively impact the overall perception of the school environment.

Research suggests that cleanliness perception goes beyond physical conditions. A study (Liu, 2017) found that people rated public washrooms as cleaner when they knew the recent cleaning time, even if they hadn't witnessed the cleaning itself. This highlights the psychological aspect of cleanliness perception. In a school setting, chronically neglected restrooms could lead students and staff to infer a generally less cared-for environment, potentially affecting their well-being.

Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Assessment Delivery

Table 5 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of assessment delivery.

Item No. 8 which states, "The teacher maintains total silence during exam days" got the highest mean score of 4.52, interpreted as "very great extent". Meanwhile, Item No. 9 which states, "The students are given the option to tell the teacher what test type they like" got the lowest mean score of 2.96, interpreted as "moderate extent". The overall mean score was 4.00, interpreted as "great extent".

The result of the study implies that maintaining silence during exams is a teacher's strength, however, student involvement in choosing assessments needs improvement. While considering student preferences can be beneficial, limitations beyond teachers'

control, such as standardized testing, may dictate test formats. This reinforces the importance of effective assessment practices, as highlighted in various studies.

Furthermore, research by Xu and Brown (2016) emphasizes the need to move beyond a basic understanding of assessment and integrate it with real-world teaching situations. Their work highlights the importance of considering factors like educational policies and cultural values that can influence assessment practices. This broader perspective on teacher assessment literacy (TALiP) acknowledges the complexities teachers face and aims to equip them with the knowledge and skills to navigate these challenges effectively.

Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Instructional Delivery According to Age

Table 6 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of instructional delivery according to age.

Item No. 2 which states, “Teacher always ask students if they have questions before proceeding to the next topic” got the highest mean score of 4.67 for younger respondents and 4.69 for older respondents, both were interpreted as “very great extent”. Meanwhile, Item No. 3 which states, “One day before discussing the topic, the teacher assigns students to read in advance - at home or the library” got the lowest mean score of 3.55 for younger respondents interpreted it as “great extent”, while Item No. 6 which states, “the teacher can manage to provide anecdotes to ease tension and boredom” got the lowest mean score of 3.91 for older respondents interpreted as “great extent”. The overall mean scores were 4.03 for younger and 4.17 for older respondents, both were interpreted as “great extent”.

The result of the study showed that the younger respondents were greatly concerned that some teachers were not giving advance reading assignments for the next topic while the older group were concerned with the teachers’ inability to inject anecdotes to break the ice during classes.

Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Instructional Delivery According to Sex

Table 7 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of instructional delivery according to sex.

Item No. 2 which states, “Teacher always ask students if they have questions before” got the highest mean score of 4.63 for male respondents and 4.71 for female respondents, both were interpreted as “very great extent”. Meanwhile, Item No. 6 which states, “the teacher can manage to provide anecdotes to ease tension and boredom” got the lowest mean score of 3.71 for male respondents, interpreted as “great extent”, while Item No. 3 which states, “One day before discussing the topic, the teacher assigns students to read in advance - at home or the library” got the lowest mean score of 3.75

for male respondents were both interpreted as “great extent”, while Item No. 3 which states, “One day before discussing the topic, the teacher assigns students to read in advance - at home or the library” got the lowest mean score of 3.75 for female respondents interpreted as “great extent”. The overall mean scores were 4.06 for male and 4.13 for female respondents, both were interpreted as “great extent”.

The result of the study showed that some teachers are unable to crack jokes to break the usual boredom in the classroom, according to the male group while the female group was mostly concerned that some teachers are unable to provide advanced reading materials for the next day’s lesson.

When teachers share a laugh or a smile with students, they help students feel more comfortable and open to learning. Using humor brings enthusiasm, positive feelings, and optimism to the classroom (McNeely, 2017).

Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Instructional Delivery According to GAS and HUMSS

Table 8 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of instructional delivery according to GAS and HUMSS.

Item No. 2 which states, “Teacher always ask students if they have questions before proceeding to the next topic” got the highest mean score of 4.89 for GAS and 4.70 for HUMSS respondents, both were interpreted as “very great extent”. Meanwhile, Item No. 6 which states “The teacher can manage to provide anecdotes to ease tension and boredom” got the lowest mean score of 3.61 for the GAS group, interpreted as “great extent”, while Item No. 3 which states, “One day before discussing the topic, the teacher assigns students to read in advance - at home or the library” got the lowest score of 3.85 for HUMSS group, interpreted as “great extent”. The overall mean scores were 4.04 for the GAS group and 4.16 for the HUMSS group, both were interpreted as “great extent”.

The results showed that across all tracks, the respondents were concerned that some of their teachers could not crack a joke to break the monotony of the usual classroom routine. At times, there is a need to inject some humor into the class, no matter how serious the discussion, to allow learners to breathe fresh air. Breaking the usual monotony of class discussion keeps the class more engaged.

According to McNeely (2017), humor can be a valuable tool for teachers to create a more enthusiastic, positive, and optimistic learning environment in the classroom.

Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Instructional Delivery According to ABM and STEM

Table 9 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of instructional delivery according to ABM and STEM.

Item No. 2 which states, “Teacher always ask students if they have questions before proceeding to the next topic” got the highest mean score of 4.69 for ABM, interpreted as “great extent” and 4.45 for STEM respondents, interpreted as “great extent”. Meanwhile, Item No. 6 which states “The teacher can manage to provide anecdotes to ease tension and boredom” got the lowest mean score of 3.83 for ABM, interpreted as “great extent”. In contrast, Item No. 3 which states, “One day before discussing the topic, the teacher assigns students to read in advance - at home or the library” got the lowest 3.50 for STEM, interpreted as “great extent”. The overall mean scores were 4.14 for the ABM group and 3.98 for the STEM group, both were interpreted as “great extent”.

The results showed that respondents across all tracks expressed a desire for more humor in their teachers' instructional styles. They felt that incorporating humor, even during serious discussions, could provide a welcome break for learners and improve engagement by alleviating the monotony of classroom routines.

Every teacher’s goal is to be effective in the classroom and help students learn. Educators want their students to be eager and engaged. Humor has the power to fuel that engagement (Aranda and Zamora, 2016).

Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Instructional Delivery According to TVL, Arts & Design, and Sports

Table 10 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of instructional delivery according to TVL, Arts & Design, and Sports.

Item No. 2 which states. “Teacher always asks students if they have questions before proceeding to the next topic” got the highest mean score of 4.66 for the TVL group and 4.64 for both Arts & Design and Sports group, all were interpreted as “very great extent”. Meanwhile. Item No. 3 which states, “One day before discussing the topic, the teacher assigns students to read in advance - at home or the library” got the lowest 3.91 for the TVL group, interpreted as “great extent” and 2.45 for the Sports group, interpreted as “low extent”, while Item No. 1 which states, “Lesson contents are delivered with corresponding visual aids or video clips” got the lowest mean score of 3.36 for Arts & Design group, interpreted as “moderate extent. The overall mean scores were 4.20 for TVL, 4.03 for Arts and Design, and 3.51 for Sports group, all were interpreted as “great extent”.

The findings revealed a common concern among students across all tracks regarding instructional delivery. Many students expressed dissatisfaction with the lack of advanced reading guides or assignments for upcoming topics. This finding suggests that students value knowing what to expect for future lessons, potentially to prepare more effectively. This highlights the importance of effective lesson planning, as emphasized by Naade & Okwelle (2018). Effective lesson plans can include providing students with

advance notice of upcoming topics and learning objectives. A well-prepared teacher can create engaging experiences that promote student understanding. However, developing these lessons requires a significant investment of time and effort. This is particularly true for new teachers who are still honing their pedagogical skills. New teachers should be committed to dedicating the necessary time to crafting effective lesson plans, which will ultimately benefit their students' learning journey.

Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Classroom Management According to Age

Table 11 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of classroom management according to age.

Item No. 2 which states, “Our classroom has a homey atmosphere – curtains, tables, etc.” got the highest mean score of 4.42 for the younger group, interpreted as “great extent”, while Item No. 3 which states, “Cleanliness of the classroom is properly maintained” got the highest mean score of 4.39 for the older group, interpreted as “great extent”. Meanwhile, Item No. 9 which states, “We have a storage cabinet for our raincoats, umbrellas or boots during the rainy season” got the lowest mean score of 1.73 for the younger group, interpreted as “low extent”, while Item No. 7 which states, “Soap, tissue papers, and others are available inside our classroom toilet” got the lowest mean score of 2.08 for the older group, interpreted as “low extent”. The overall mean scores were 3.41 for the younger group, interpreted as “moderate extent” and 3.54 for the older group, interpreted as “great extent”.

In terms of classroom management, the respondents were concerned that tissue papers, soaps, and the like are not available all the time and also the older respondents indicated that there is no available cabinet or rack for their raincoats and umbrellas during the rainy season. These can be easily corrected with proper coordination with the parents.

Teachers often find that building strong relationships with students helps prevent classroom disruptions. The study found that classrooms where teachers focused on building and maintaining good relationships with students had a big improvement. Students were 33% more engaged in lessons, and there were 75% fewer disruptions. (Terada, 2019).

Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Classroom Management According to Sex

Table 12 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of classroom management according to sex.

Item No. 3 which states, “Cleanliness of the classroom is properly maintained” got the highest mean score of 4.31 for the male group, interpreted as “great extent”, while Items No. 2 and 3 which states, “Our classroom has a homey atmosphere – curtains, tables, etc.” and “Cleanliness of the classroom is properly maintained” got the highest

mean score of 4.40 for the female group, interpreted as “great extent”. Meanwhile, Item No. 7 which states, “Soap, tissue papers, and others are available inside our classroom toilet” got the lowest mean score of 2.02 for the male group, interpreted as “low extent”, while Item No. 9 which states, “We have a storage cabinet for our raincoats, umbrellas or boots during the rainy season” got the lowest mean score of 1.87 for the female group, interpreted as “low extent”. The overall mean scores were 3.50 for the male group, interpreted as “great extent” and 3.46 for the female group, interpreted as “moderate extent”.

This implies that regardless of their gender, the respondents indicated concern for the lack of the necessary toiletries in their toilets and the lack of storage cabinets for raincoats, umbrellas, or boots during the rainy season. Supply must have been affected by the availability of funds, in this part, PTA support may be needed.

Effective teaching and learning process is directly or indirectly influenced by organized classroom management. By establishing clear routines and minimizing disruptions, teachers can create a more structured learning environment, which paves the way for deeper student engagement (Mastul and Hajilan, 2017).

Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Classroom Management According to GAS and HUMSS

Table 13 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of classroom management according to GAS and HUMSS.

Item No. 5 which states, “Blackboards, bulletin boards, and the teachers’ table and chair are always clean and in place” got the highest mean score of 4.29 for the GAS group, interpreted as “great extent”, while Item No. 2 which states, “Our classroom has a homey atmosphere – curtains, tables, etc.” got the highest mean score of 4.46 for HUMSS, interpreted as “great extent”. Meanwhile, Item No. 7 which states, “Soap, tissue papers, and others are available inside our classroom toilet” got the lowest mean score of 1.75 for the GAS group, interpreted as “low extent”, while Item No. 9 which states, “We have a storage cabinet for our raincoats, umbrellas or boots during the rainy season” got the lowest mean score of 1.53 for HUMSS group, interpreted as “low extent”. The overall mean scores were 3.43 for GAS and 3.42 for the HUMSS group, both were interpreted as “moderate extent”.

This implies that regardless of their tracks, the respondents have the same concern over the lack of toiletries in their toilets. These needs could critically affect hygiene and sanitation and they must be addressed on time.

The complexities of classroom management demand awareness, patience, good timing, the ability to set clear boundaries, and a touch of intuition. Guiding a diverse group of students with varying interests and attention spans on a path to meaningful learning is a challenging, yet rewarding endeavor. (Rabadi and Ray, 2017).

Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Classroom Management According to ABM and STEM

Table 14 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of classroom management according to ABM and STEM.

Item No. 3 which states, "Cleanliness of the classroom is properly maintained" got the highest mean score of 4.44 for the ABM group, interpreted as "great extent", while Item No 2 which states, "Our classroom has a homey atmosphere - curtains, tables, etc." got the highest mean score of 4.60 for STEM, interpreted as "great extent". Meanwhile, Item No. 7 which states, "Soap, tissue papers, and others are available inside our classroom toilet" got the lowest mean score of 2.00 for the ABM group, interpreted as "low extent" and 2.50 for the STEM group, interpreted as "moderate extent". The overall mean scores were 3.48 for ABM, interpreted as "moderate extent" and 3.69 for the STEM group, interpreted as "great extent".

This implies that regardless of their tracks, the respondents have the same concern over the lack of toiletries in their toilets. These needs could critically affect hygiene and sanitation and they must be addressed on time.

Schools hold a central role in a child's life, shaping their intellectual development and social skills. Beyond academics, student health and safety remain paramount concerns for both parents and school administrators. Germs and bacteria can readily spread in classrooms, cafeterias, restrooms, libraries, playgrounds, and other school spaces, highlighting the importance of consistent cleaning and sanitation practices. A growing body of research underscores the significant influence of the school environment on student outcomes. Studies suggest that factors like cleanliness, safety, and overall atmosphere can positively or negatively impact both academic performance and student well-being (Lawson et al., 2017).

Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Classroom Management According to TVL, Arts & Design, and Sports

Table 15 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of classroom management according to TVL, Arts & Design, and Sports.

Item No. 1 which states, "The room is very conducive for learning" got the highest mean score of 4.48 for the TVL group, interpreted as "great extent", while Item No 3 which states, "Cleanliness of the classroom is properly maintained" got the highest mean score of 4.64 for Arts & Design group, interpreted as "very great extent" and Item No. 5 which states, "Blackboards, bulletin boards, and the teacher's table and chair are always clean and in place" got the highest mean score of 4.27 for Sports group, interpreted as "great extent". Meanwhile, Item No. 9 which states, "We have a storage cabinet for our raincoats,

umbrellas or boots during the rainy season” got the lowest mean score of 1.73 for the TVL group, interpreted as “low extent”; Item No. 7 which states, “Soap, tissue papers, and others are available inside our classroom toilet” got the lowest mean score of 1.50 for Arts & Design group, interpreted as “low extent” and Item No. 6 which states, “We have a clean CR inside the classroom” 2.09 for Sport group, interpreted as “low extent”. The overall mean scores were 3.52 for TVL, interpreted as “great extent”, while 3.49 for the Arts & Design group and 3.35 for the Sports group, both were interpreted as “moderate extent”.

This implies that a core concern for the respondents is ensuring proper health and sanitation within classrooms. Equipping students with the necessary toiletries, like soap, toilet paper, and others, is fundamental. Without these supplies, it's akin to lacking a clear sanitation plan for the students. They wouldn't have the means to maintain good hygiene throughout the day, potentially compromising their health and the overall classroom environment.

In a study conducted in Botswana's Ngamiland district, researchers supported this notion (Thakadu et al., 2018). Their findings highlighted the importance of hygiene education in primary schools for preventing the spread of diseases. However, the study also revealed that a lack of proper sanitation facilities and supplies can hinder hygiene practices. This reinforces the importance of providing essential toiletries in classrooms.

Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Assessment Delivery According to Age

Table 16 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of assessment delivery according to age.

Item No. 8 which states, “The teacher maintains total silence during exam days” got the highest mean score of 4.45 for the younger group, interpreted as “great extent” and 4.58 for the older group, interpreted as “very great extent”. Meanwhile, Item No. 9 which states, “The students are given the option to tell the teacher what test type they like” got the lowest mean score of 2.76 for the younger group and 3.14 for the older group, both were interpreted as “moderate extent”. The overall mean scores were 3.92 for the younger group and 4.06 for the older group, both were interpreted as “great extent”.

With regards to assessment delivery, the main concern of the respondents across age groups is that they are not truly given the option to suggest what type of exam is best for them. For short quizzes and daily tasks, this concern may be valid. However, for long tests and other exams, teachers may not have the option to accommodate learners' requests regarding assessment types. Regardless of the assessment format, providing students with effective feedback is crucial for their learning.

Students become actively involved in evaluating their learning when they receive descriptive feedback throughout the learning process. A study by Garrison and Ehringhaus (2019) highlights this type of feedback as one of the most effective tools for

advancing student progress. Effective descriptive feedback goes beyond just grades, stickers, or generic praise like "good job!" Instead, it offers specific details about what students are doing well in relation to the learning objectives. This feedback also provides clear guidance for improvement, outlining the next steps students can take to move forward. By receiving such focused and actionable feedback, students gain valuable insights into their learning journey, allowing them to understand their current level and propelling them toward future growth.

Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Assessment Delivery According to Sex

Table 17 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of assessment delivery according to sex.

Item No. 8 which states, "The teacher maintains total silence during exam days" got the highest mean score of 4.51 for the male group and 4.52 for the female group, both were interpreted as "very great extent". Meanwhile, Item No. 9 which states, "The students are given the option to tell the teacher what test type they like" got the lowest mean score of 3.27 for the male group and 2.76 for the older group, both were interpreted as "moderate extent". The overall mean scores were 4.06 for the male group and 3.96 for the female group, both were interpreted as "great extent".

The study revealed that learners are still looking at the possibility that they will be given the chance to suggest or pick their exam types but unfortunately, teachers have limited options as to the kind of assessment to be administered.

Formative assessment isn't something teachers tack onto instruction; it's the very foundation of effective teaching. It's about continuously gathering information on student learning, but more importantly, what teachers do with that information. The key lies in how they use this valuable insight to improve their teaching and actively engage students in their learning journey. This might involve adapting teaching methods based on student needs or sharing feedback in a way that empowers students to take ownership of their progress (Garrison and Ehringhaus, 2019).

Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Assessment Delivery According to GAS and HUMSS

Table 18 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of assessment delivery according to GAS and HUMMS.

Item No. 8 which states, "The teacher maintains total silence during exam days" got the highest mean score of 4.68 for the GAS group and 4.57 for the HUMSS group, both were interpreted as "very great extent". Meanwhile, Item No. 9 which states, "The students are given the option to tell the teacher what test type they like" got the lowest

mean score of 3.18 for the GAS group and 2.87 for the HUMMS group, both were interpreted as “moderate extent”. The overall mean scores were 4.23 for the GAS group and 3.95 for the HUMSS group, both were interpreted as “great extent”.

This indicates that learners are not given a free hand to pick what options they prefer with the assessments. The option for students to pick their assessment type is not a traditional practice, but in some private universities, it is an open practice. With public schools in the Philippines, particularly with long tests, it is the SDO that decides on the kind of assessments that must be administered.

However, the world of education is filled with various types of assessment, from standardized state tests to classroom quizzes. While concerns exist about potential testing overuse, a crucial shift in perspective is needed (Garrison and Ehringhaus, 2019). Effective assessment goes beyond simply measuring achievement; it's about gathering valuable information on student learning. The more comprehensive this data is, the clearer picture educators gain of student strengths, weaknesses, and areas needing further support. This allows educators to tailor instruction and interventions to meet individual student needs, ultimately promoting deeper learning.

Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Assessment Delivery According to ABM and STEM

Table 19 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of assessment delivery according to ABM and STEM.

Item No. 8 which states, “The teacher maintains total silence during exam days” got the highest mean score of 4.39 for the ABM group, interpreted as “great extent”, while Item No. 4 which states, “Exams and long quizzes are being discussed in the class” got the highest mean score of 4.55 for STEM group, interpreted as “very great extent”. Meanwhile, Item No. 9 which states, “The students are given the option to tell the teacher what test type they like” got the lowest mean score of 3.33 for the ABM group and 2.65 for the STEM group, both were interpreted as “moderate extent”. The overall mean scores were 4.06 for the ABM group and 3.98 for the STEM group, both were interpreted as “great extent”.

Across all tracks, the learners indicated that they are having some issues with their inability to choose or suggest what exam types they prefer. On one hand, it has not been established that learners' preferred type can guarantee higher exam results.

Garrison and Ehringhaus (2019) believe that most successful middle schools engage students in all aspects of their learning. There are many strategies for accomplishing this. One such strategy is student-led conferences. To ensure student-led conferences present a balanced view of strengths and weaknesses, educators can leverage a combination of summative and formative assessment data alongside student self-reflection.

Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Assessment Delivery According to TVL, Arts & Design, and Sports

Table 20 shows the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of assessment delivery according to TVL, Arts & Design, and Sports.

Item No. 8 which states, “The teacher maintains total silence during exam days” got the highest mean score of 4.60 for the TVL group, interpreted as “very great extent”; 4.36 for Arts & Design and 4.18 for Sports, both were interpreted as “great extent”. Meanwhile, Item No. 9 which states, “The students are given the option to tell the teacher what test type they like” got the lowest mean score of 2.91 for the TVL group, 2.64 for the Arts & Design group, and 3.09 for Sports group, all were interpreted as “moderate extent”. The overall mean scores were 4.03 for the TVL group, 3.81 for the Arts & Design group, and 3.66 for the Sports group, all were interpreted as “great extent”.

The results showed that across all tracks students are aiming to have their exam type considered but it appeared that none of their options could be followed.

According to Anderson (2017), a study investigated the impact of formative assessment training on student achievement. The study involved 22 Year 4 mathematics teachers from a Swedish municipality who participated in a professional development program focused on formative assessment. This program emphasized a unified approach incorporating various strategies. The research examined how changes in teachers' classroom practices following the program affected student achievement. Results showed that, after controlling for pretest scores, classes in the intervention group significantly outperformed the control group in a post-test administered one school year later. This study contributes to our understanding of the under-studied areas of professional development in formative assessment and the impact of teacher practice based on a unified approach to formative assessment strategies.

Level of Students' Academic Performance when They Are Grouped According to Variables

Table 21 shows the level of students' performance when grouped according to variables.

When grouped according to age, the younger group has a mean score of 86.28 and 86.51 for the older group, both were interpreted as “very satisfactory”. When grouped according to sex, the male group has a mean score of 86.81 and 86.13 for the female group, both were interpreted as “very satisfactory”. When grouped according to track, the STEM group obtained a mean score of 92.30, interpreted as “outstanding” while the Sports group had a mean score of 83.27, interpreted as “satisfactory”.

STEM appeared to have garnered the best academic performance from amongst, as they reached the “outstanding” level. When grouped according to aforementioned variables, the results of the study showed that each track fairly had the same effort as they all showed a “very satisfactory” level.

Difference in the Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Instructional Delivery When they are Grouped and Compared According to Age, Sex, and Track

Table 22 shows the comparative analysis in the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of instructional delivery according to variables.

When grouped according to sex, the male group has a mean score of 120.66 and 132.81 for the female group, the computed U-test was 7036.00 and the p-value was 0.197, which is higher than the significance level of 0.05, interpreted as “not significant”.

Thus, the hypothesis that states, “there is no significant difference in the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students’ in the area of instructional delivery according to sex” was therefore “accepted”.

This implies that sex does not significantly affect the opinion of the respondents in assessing the teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of instructional delivery.

When grouped according to age, the younger group has a mean score of 114.01 and 140.11 for the older group, the computed U-test was 6250.00 and the p-value was 0.006, which is lower than the significance level of 0.05, interpreted as “significant”. When grouped according to track, the GAS group has a mean score of 118.66; 136.99 for HUMSS; 133.51 for ABM; 106.40 for STEM; 139.75 for TVL; 113.18 for Arts & Design, and 55.77 for Sports, the computed H-test was 16.43 and the p-value was 0.012, it is lower than the significance level of 0.05, interpreted as “significant”.

Thus, the hypothesis that states, “there is no significant difference in the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of instructional delivery according to age and track” was therefore “rejected”.

This implies that age and track significantly affect the opinion of the respondents in assessing the teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of instructional delivery. As the results revealed, the older respondents appeared to have a higher expectation of their teacher for them to consider the latter as truly competent. On the other hand, the respondents belonging to TVL were highly expectant of their teacher's specialized skills.

According to Aranda and Zamora (2016), a study explored the use of differentiated instruction to improve student academic performance in a Filipino language class at the

National University. The researchers highlighted the challenge educators face in creating environments that cater to diverse learning styles within a classroom. They proposed that differentiated instruction, tailored to individual student needs, could address this challenge. The study's purpose was to investigate the effectiveness of differentiated instruction on the academic performance of grade ten students.

Difference in the Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Classroom Management When they are Grouped and Compared According to Age, Sex, and Track

Table 23 shows the comparative analysis in the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of classroom management according to variables.

When grouped according to sex, the male group has a mean score of 132.71 and 124.91 for the female group, the computed U-test was 7301.00 and the p-value was 0.408, it is higher than the significance level of 0.05, interpreted as “not significant”. When grouped according to track, the GAS group has a mean score of 119.23; 122.97 for HUMMS; 129.47 for ABM; 160.60 for STEM; 130.20 for TVL; 134.11 for Arts & Design, and 101.18 for SPORTS, the computed H-test was 6.32 and the p-value was 0.388, it is higher than the significance level of 0.05, interpreted as “not significant”.

Thus, the hypothesis that states, “there is no significant difference in the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of classroom management according to sex and track” was therefore “accepted”.

This implies that sex and track do not significantly affect the opinion of the respondents in assessing the teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of classroom management.

When grouped according to age, the younger group has a mean score of 118.31 and 137.03 for the older group, the computed U-test was 6926.50 and the p-value was 0.042, which is lower than the significance level of 0.05, interpreted as “significant”.

Thus, the hypothesis that states, “there is no significant difference in the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by the student in the area of classroom management according to age and track” was therefore “rejected”.

This implies that age significantly affects how respondents assess their senior high school teachers' classroom management skills. As learners get older, they become more sensitive to the classroom environment. What might be acceptable to younger students might not be for older ones.

This heightened sensitivity aligns with research on healthy classroom systems. Studies like the one by Barrett et al. (2017) emphasize the importance of factors like indoor air quality, lighting, and acoustics. This research delves deeper by investigating

how design principles can influence these aspects of the classroom environment. Their findings suggest that optimizing design features like lighting, temperature, and air quality can significantly contribute to a healthy learning environment, ultimately impacting learning outcomes.

Difference in the Extent of Teaching Competence of Senior High School Teachers as Assessed by Students in the Area of Assessment Delivery When they are Grouped and Compared According to Age, Sex, and Track

Table 24 shows the comparative analysis in the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of assessment delivery according to variables.

When grouped according to sex, the male group has a mean score of 137.51 and 121.76 for the female group, the computed U-test was 6816.00 and the p-value was 0.095, which is higher than the significance level of 0.05, interpreted as “not significant”. When grouped according to track, the GAS group has a mean score of 118.66; 136.99 for HUMMS; 133.51 for ABM; 106.40 for STEM; 139.75 for TVL; 133.18 for Arts & Design, and 55.77 for Sports, the computed H-test was 12.38 and the p-value was 0.054, it is higher than the significance level of 0.05, interpreted as “not significant”.

Thus, the hypothesis that states, “there is no significant difference in the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of assessment delivery according to sex and track” was therefore “accepted”.

This implies that sex and track do not significantly affect the opinion of the respondents in assessing the teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of assessment delivery.

When grouped according to age, the younger group has a mean score of 117.19 and 138.07 for the older group, the computed U-test was 6788.50 and the p-value was 0.024, which is lower than the significance level of 0.05, interpreted as “significant”.

Thus, the hypothesis that states, “there is no significant difference in the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of assessment delivery according to age and track” was therefore “rejected”.

This implies that age significantly affects the opinion of the respondents in assessing the teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by students in the area of assessment delivery.

The term "assessment" encompasses a wide range of practices, from large-scale standardized tests to informal classroom checks. This broad use can lead to concerns about over-testing. To address this, educators can shift their perspective by viewing all testing as a form of assessment, and ultimately, as a way to gather information. The

more comprehensive this information is, the clearer picture we gain of student achievement and areas needing improvement (Garrison & Ehringhaus, 2019).

Difference on the Level of Students' Academic Performance when they are Grouped and Compared According to Age, Sex, and Track

Table 25 shows the comparative analysis in the level of academic performance of senior high school teachers as assessed by students when they are grouped and compared according to variables.

When grouped according to age, the younger group has a mean score of 125.57 and 130.26 for the older group, the computed U-test was 7819.50 and the p-value was 0.611, which is higher than the significance level of 0.05, interpreted as "not significant". When grouped according to sex, the male group has a mean score of 13.72 and 122.94 for the female group, the computed U-test was 6997.00 and the p-value was 0.174, it is higher than the significance level of 0.05, interpreted as "not significant".

Thus, the hypothesis that states, "there is no significant difference in the level of academic performance of senior high school teachers as assessed by students when they are grouped and compared according to sex and age" was therefore "accepted".

This implies that age and sex do not significantly affect the level of academic performance of senior high school students.

When grouped according to track, the GAS group has a mean score of 143.30; 141.35 for HUMSS; 133.69 for ABM; 234.68 for STEM; 87.93 for TVL; 91.43 for Arts & Design, and 72.32 for Sports, the computed H-test was 75.34 and the p-value was 0.000, it is lower than the significance level of 0.05, interpreted as "significant".

Thus, the hypothesis that states, "there is no significant difference in the level of academic performance of senior high school teachers as assessed by students when they are grouped and compared according to track" was therefore "rejected".

This implies that track significantly affects the level of academic performance of senior high school students.

According to Gbollie and Keamu (2017), students' motivation, learning strategies, and academic performance are interconnected. Their study found that students placed the most value on motivational beliefs associated with extrinsic goals, meaning they were most motivated by external rewards. Interestingly, students also reported the lowest levels of test anxiety. When it came to learning strategies, rehearsal techniques, like memorization, were the most commonly used. In contrast, seeking help from teachers or peers was the least frequently employed strategy. The research also revealed significant correlations between motivation and learning strategies. Furthermore, the study identified factors that hinder learning and concluded with recommendations for improving student performance.

Relationship Between the Extent of Teaching Competence and the Level of Students' Academic Performance

Table 26 shows the relational analysis between the extent of teaching competence and the level of students' academic performance.

The extent of teaching competence and the level of student's academic performance has a computed rho-value of 0.020 and a p-value of 0.756, it is higher than the level of significance of 0.05, interpreted as "not significant".

Hence, the hypothesis that states, "there is no significant relationship between the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers and students' academic performance" was therefore "accepted".

This implies that the extent of teaching competence does not significantly affect the student's academic performance. This could be due to the fact that today's learners are mostly digitally inclined and even with their sedentary lifestyle, their access to the internet and some advanced gadgets allows them to do self-studying. This means that learners' dependence on teachers to facilitate learning may have been reduced.

Naz (2016), conducted a study to see the "Effects of Teachers Professional Competence on Students Academic Achievements at Secondary School level in Muzaffarabad District" in the light of National Professional Standards for Teachers. It was found that male and female teachers were competent. There was a significant difference between male teachers' professional competence scores and female teachers' professional competence scores. It was found that there was a difference between male students' achievement scores and female students' achievement scores. It was recommended that teachers might be trained according to professional standards. IT facilities, libraries, books, helping material, etc. might be provided to teachers.

Conclusions

The extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables showed that (a) Some teachers are not giving advance reading guides or materials for the next day's topic. It can be concluded that some teachers are not readily prepared to provide pre-discussion reading assignments to learners. (b) Soaps and toiletries are not available in the classroom's toilet. It can be drawn out of this result that funds for the supply of the said toiletries is an issue.

To establish the extent of teaching competence of senior high school teachers as assessed by the students when grouped according to the aforementioned variables showed the same set of concerns as follows: (a) Teachers are not giving advance reading materials or clues for the next days' lessons. It can be concluded that the learners are

mostly preparing for the next day's lessons and their anticipatory moves may not have been sensed by their teachers. (b) Toiletries are not available in the classroom's toilet. It can be concluded that there is no consistent source of funding for these toiletries to be supplied as needed.

The results of the learner's performance are indicative of their academic capabilities but based on the results, it can be drawn that tracks like TVL, Sports, and Arts need more study time to keep up and get through a satisfactory level.

There was a significant difference in the extent of teacher's competence of senior high school teachers when grouped according to age. This means that the opinion of the younger respondents differs largely from the opinion of older respondents. The older respondents take into account the competence of their teachers in almost all teaching aspects and they believe in their competence while the younger respondents take things lightly. As such, competence among their teachers is like any other ordinary thing teachers do.

There was a significant relationship between the extent of teaching competence and the level of student academic performance. This means that the more competent the teachers, the academic performance of learners is expected to be higher as well.

Recommendations

The findings of the study indicated that some teachers are not providing advanced reading materials/assignments to learners for them to study for the next day's discussion. It is recommended that teachers provide an advanced course guide at the onset of the class each year to provide students with a heads-up on what to prepare or read.

The finding also showed that soap and tissue paper are not regularly available inside the toilet. It is recommended that teachers and the classroom PTA officers collaborate to discuss funding sources. The PTA may decide to provide the funds for toiletries to the homeroom teacher or supply directly the said needs. There is also an option for the teachers or parents to tap additional donors who can help provide the toiletries.

The results also showed that the performance of TVL, Sports, and Arts tracks were all at the bottom with satisfactory levels. It is recommended that teachers' competence in handling these specialized subjects be measured through a calibration test. A course-specific training may then be provided for teachers handling these subjects.

There was a significant difference extent of teaching competence when respondents were grouped according to age across all areas. It can be recommended that yearly in-service training focusing on teaching styles and instructional delivery be given to teachers.

There was a significant relationship between the extent of teachers' competence and the level of learners' academic performance. This means there is a need to ensure that teaching skills and instructional competence are at their highest level because learners' performance could be greatly affected. There is a need for teachers to be regularly trained and there is also a need to make sure that teachers can pursue their postgraduate studies to remain on top of the game.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher prioritized ethical considerations throughout the study. As human respondents were involved, the research ensured the confidentiality of their information and respected their dignity. Additionally, the study minimized any potential risks to the respondents.

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REFERENCES

- Anderson, Catarina. (2017). The impact of formative assessment on student achievement: A study of the effects of changes to classroom practice after a comprehensive professional development Program. *Learning and Instruction*. Volume 49, No. 1, pp. 92-102.
- Aranda, Ma. Rita and Zamora, Joel. (2016). *Using Differentiated Instruction in Improving the Academic Performance of Students in Filipino Language*. National University, Manila.
- Barrett, P., Davies, F., Zhang, Y., & Barrett, L. (2015). The impact of classroom design on pupils' learning: Final results of a holistic, multi-level analysis. *Building and Environment*, 89, pp. 118-133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2015.02.013>
- Bilasa, Ritchie. (2017). *Teacher Competencies and Its Relation to Academic Performance of the Selected Grade 10 Students in MAPEH of San Isidro National High School S.Y. 2015-2016*. Undergraduate Thesis, Polytechnic University of the Philippines.
- Clark, L. A., & Watson, D. (2019). Constructing validity: New developments in creating objective measuring instruments. *Psychological Assessment*, 31(12), pp. 1412–1427. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pas0000626>
- De Franzo, Susan. (2015). *Why Use Demographic Questions in Surveys?* Published online by Snapsurveys. <https://www.snapsurveys.com/blog/demographics-questions-surveys/>
- Ferguson, C. J. (2016). *An introduction to statistical reasoning* (9th ed.). Nelson Education.

- Garrison, Catherine and Ehringhaus, Michael. (2019). *Formative and Summative Assessments in the Classroom*. Measured Progress. Association for Middle Level Education. Columbus, Ohio.
- Gbollie, C., & Keamu, H. P. (2017). Student academic performance: The role of motivation, strategies, and perceived factors hindering Liberian junior and senior high school students' learning. *Education Research International*, 2017, 1789084. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/1789084>
- Goldhaber, D., Lavery, L., & Theobald, R. (2015). Uneven playing field? Assessing the teacher quality gap between advantaged and disadvantaged students. *Educational Researcher*, 44(5), pp. 293-307. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X15592622>
- Gravetter, F. J., & Wallnau, L. B. (2017). *Statistics for the behavioral sciences* (10th ed.). Cengage Learning. Pp. 70-78.
- Lawson, H. B., Dollard, M. M., & Bradshaw, C. P. (2017). School safety: A review of the literature on school climate, peer relationships, and school violence prevention. *Professional School Counseling*, 11(1), pp. 31-49. <https://bera-journals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/rev3.3043>.
- Liu, Y. S. (2017). Effects of dynamic information display on the perception of public washroom cleanliness. *Smart Construction Research*, 1(2).
- Mastul, Al-Rashiff & Hajilan, Kaberi O. (2017). Secondary School Teachers' Classroom Management Practices: Their Implications for the Academic Performance of Grade 10 Students. *Journal of Social Sciences (COES&RJ-JSS)*. Vol. 6, No. 3, pp. 558-583.
- McNeely, R. (2017). Using humor in the classroom: Laughter has the power to fuel engagement and help students learn. National Education Association. <https://www.nea.org/tools/52165.htm>
- Mellinger, C. D., & Hanson, T. A. (2017). *Quantitative Research Methods in Translation and Interpreting Studies*. Routledge. Pp. 167-177.
- Naade, Noble and Okwelle, Paulinus (2018). Towards Improving Teachers' Competences in the Use of Instructional Materials in Senior Secondary Schools' Physics in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. *International Journal of Innovative Education Research*. Volume 6, No. 1, pp 77-85,
- Naz, Kishwar. (2016). Effects of teachers' professional competence on students' academic achievements at secondary school level in Muzaffarabad District. *Educational Leadership Manual*.
- Oducado, R. M. F. (2020). Survey instrument validation rating scale. West Visayas State University.
- Pallant, J. (2016). *SPSS survival manual: A step by step guide to data analysis using SPSS* (6th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
- Rabadi, S., & Ray, B. (2017). 5 Principles of Outstanding Classroom Management. <https://www.edutopia.org/article/5-principles-outstanding-classroom-management>
- Sickler, Angela. (2017). Study Strategies for Before, During, and After Class. *Faculty Focus in Teaching and Learning*. <https://www.facultyfocus.com/articles/teaching-and-learning/study-strategies-class/>.
- Thakadu, O. T., Ngwenya, B. N., Phaladze, N. A., & Bolaane, B. (2018). Sanitation and hygiene practices among primary school learners in Ngamiland district,

- Botswana. *Physics and Chemistry of the Earth, Parts A/B/C*, 105, pp. 224-230.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pce.2018.02.006> [Pergamon]
- Terada, Youki. (2019). *The Key to Effective Classroom Management A three-phase process helps build strong teacher-student bonds, which can reduce disruptive behavior*. Geroge Lucas Educational Foundation.
<https://www.edutopia.org/article/key-effective-classroom-management>
- The Wing Institute. (2018). *Teacher Competencies*.
<https://www.winginstitute.org/quality-teachers-compentencies>.
- Xu, Y., & Brown, G. T. L. (2016). Teacher assessment literacy in practice: A reconceptualization. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 58, pp. 149-162.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2016.05.010> [Pergamon]